

Textual Analysis of the Abdurauf Fitrat's Work "Oldest Turkic Literature Samples"**Literature**

Keywords: text, source, style, piece, quartet, classification, marsia, comedy, divan, dictionary, manuscript, paragraph, translation.

Hamraeva Arzigul Djalalovna**Teacher of Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature City Tashkent, Uzbekistan.****Abstract**

Abduraf Fitrat, one of the great representatives of Uzbek literature, has studied almost all aspects of Turkic literature. His research on this path is reflected in several articles and works. Fitrat's "Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" and "Uzbek Literature Samples" are the first complexes in Uzbek literature. At the beginning of the 20th century, when printing and publishing began to spread, classic works were only available in several copies, not in one copy. The two complexes of Abdurauf Fitrat have emerged as the scientific application of these works. Studying the work of Mahmoud Koshgari's "Divan Lugat at-Turk" creates a lot of valuable information such as the language, literature, culture of Turkic peoples. The classification of the fragments in the "Divan" was studied by Fitrat and contemporary scientists. Such as A.Samoylovich, Steblova, Radlov, Brokellman, F.Kopruhu, N.Osim. However, their research was part of a certain part of "Divan". Fitrat created a special work dedicated to the Divan study. The "Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" is a collection dedicated to the fragment of the book "Divan Lugat at-Turk", founded in 1927. Scientist presented the fragmentary poetry fragments of "Devan", combined with the rhythmic nature of the poem, as a monumental work. The complex consists of 3 parts, part 1 consists of quarters, part 2 binary, part 3 is a special dictionary. The article examines the composition of the "Oldest Turkic Literature Sample", the specific style of the science of the poetic fragment, the textual study of the fragments.

Fitrat's "The Oldest Turkic Literature samples" play an important role in the scientist's scientific potential and high research ability. J.Hudoyberdiev has written in his article "Divan Lugat at-Turk: finds, translations and investigation" about "Divan Lugat at-Turk" ("Devonulug'otitturk"). [10, p. 12] Fitrat first disclosed when and where the "Divan Lugat at-Turk" was found by the first published work and the first translator RifatKilisli's article published in "Yangi Tong" newspaper. [2, p. 417-421].

RifatKilisli tried to correct some of the confusing points in the text in the preposition of "Divan Lugat at-Turk", while BasimAtalay translated [1].

There are several lithographs in the work of "Divan Lugat at-Turk" in Institute of Oriental Studies of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences, which allowed the Uzbek scholars to study "Divon" at a time when printing and publishing works began to form. Almost all lithographs have been published in Istanbul, and fragments of Fitrat's "Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" collection are based on these books. Inverter number 5201-3, a lug of 1106 pages published in 1914-1916 years, 5206-3, 5204-5, 14345-47, 8999, 9000, 5206-8 inverted numbers luggage, 20927 inverted numberin the 1333Hijri year. The 20929 invert in Hijri1335year inspired scientists like Fitrat to bring the classic samples to the reader. Here, however, we must first of all mention the unknown work of the author, which was initially important in studying the history of Divon. For the first time in this article J.Hudoyberdiev has told about the existence of this work. As we have observed, a manuscript is kept under the heading "Fahrenheit for the words" Divon dictionary with the number 5046/1 in the Manuscripts of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. Each word shows which folder the page is.

The words in the first volume of the Arabic edition are given in pages 1-57, 67-47; the second volume is given in pages 59-62, 74-83, and the third volume is in pages 62-66 and 83. According to H.Hasanov, a researcher from Divon, this indicator was created in 1924-1925 years. If this date is recognized in science, this manuscript is the first indivisible glossary based on Divon in literature. The manuscript is presented in a 190-page text containing 3 major works. The next two manuscripts in the manuscript were copied in different writing works by AlisherNavoi's "Vakfiya" and "Munshaot". In the last part of the manuscript, researcher A.Nosirov pointed out that he had published the first for the words "Divan Lugat at-Turk" in 1963, by H. Hanif. He estimates that the dictionary was created by Fitrat, but the publisher did not give any details. The manuscript is part of the manuscripts of the book Dictionary for the Divan Dictionary, and consists of the words made for every three volumes of the dictionary "Divan Lugat at-Turk". The words in the dictionary are in alphabetical order, which indicate how many times the "Divon ..." and the pages were used. The order in the dictionary consists of the words used in Chapters 1 to 2 and 3. The manuscript was rebuilt with a white cover. It is evident that the pages copied with the "Vaqfiya" and "Munshaat" are attached to the manuscript. The book "Divan Lugat at-Turk" is written in two inks: pages from "lom" letter and it is copied in black ink, and the next words are copied in dark pink ink. The page is divided into two parts and the words are written in columns. Here are the pages that are used on the page. Even the words used repeatedly on a single page have also been copied separately.

تغ 92

تغ 92

تغ 92

تغ 92.

The dictionary does not contain the meaning of the words, but they are just listed. The manuscript has been copied in the Uzbek *nastaliq* script, and some pages of the manuscript have blank pages. On such pages, the writing of the word "fitrat" has been practiced in the Latin script. This suggests that the dictionary was created on the basis of the Latin script. The dictionary begins with a few words: ب (*be*), ت (*te*), ج (*jim*), خ (*xe*), د (*dol*), ز (*zol*), س (*sin*), ش (*shin*), غ (*ge*), ق (*qof*), ك (*kof*), ل (*lom*), م (*mim*), ه (*hoyehavvaz*), ا (*alif*), ي (*yo*). Each letter is separated according to the use of the words 1, 2, and 3 before. Dictionary:

ب (Be), ا - خلد

ت 26

ت-229

پر 271

begins like that. In black ink, some of the inscriptions are included in the dark pink ink. Some words have been deleted and corrected. The following words have to be added to the words starting with the **be** letter used in Volume 2:

(?) 202 بِلْتِنْدِي

208 بِلْمِنْدِي

272 بُرْقِمَاق

274 بِلْكَزْمَاق

بُيِّنْتَمَاق 287

بُرْمُنْحَق 287

The insertion of such additives is very common. Beginning with the letter *Mim*, the words are divided into columns on page 4 and placed in very short distances. The dictionary also includes the allocation of words in terms of volumes, as well as families in their location. First, the expression "noun", "adjective", "adverb" and "pronoun" are used to describe verbs. Words related to the Verb phrase:

بُقْرَمَاق - تُقْرَمَاق 67
 تَكْرَمَك - تُكْرُر 69
 تَمْرَمَاق - تَمْرُر
 تُنْرَمَك - تُنْرُر
 تُبْزَمَك - تُبْزُر 71

are given like that. This layout is stored up to the end of the dictionary.

The location, usage, and choice of words in the dictionary will lead to the conclusion that the dictionary may have been compiled by Fitrat. In our opinion this dictionary was compiled by Fitrat. This is a case when we compare the linguistic part of the "Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" with this manuscript. The dictionary of the work may be derived from the *Fihrist* word for "Divan's Dictionary". The words read, written, especially the character of a series of words on the style of the phrase, *-mak* and *-moq* affixes' the word distribution of the core, depending on the nature reminds us of the style of work. Moreover, the order of words in the dictionary in the "Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" is in line with the definition of "Divan Lug'at" in the *Fihrist*. Fitrat did not give all the words in the "Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" and some of them were selected. For the words "divan linguist", there are 8 000 words in the *fihrist*. Another reason why the dictionary is based on Fitrat is the use of the Latin script on the manuscript pages. The dictionary should have been created earlier by Fitrat's "Oldest Turkic Literature samples". Fitrat wrote the dictionary part of the "Oldest Turkic Literature samples" using this dictionary in creative ways.

"Divan Lugat at-Turk" was learned by many scientists during the period before Fitrat. Every scientist tried to explain various aspects of the work. Attempts to classify narratives in the literature literally coincide with the beginning of the 20th century. Turkish scholars NajibAsimbek, [5, p. 46-54] FuadKusruzuza, [4, p. 71] foreign researchers Radlov, [8, p. 8-19] Brokelmann [3, p. 29, 37-39]. This classification, which is one of the earliest scholars of the Uzbek scholars and has not lost its scientific significance, belongs to Fitrat.

Fitratevaluating the work of Koshgari, he emphasizes that he is well-known in Turkish, Turkmen, Oguz, Chigil, Kyrgyz, and Kyrgyz, their rhymes, comments, folklore literature. The fragments collected on the "Oldest Turkic Literature samples" are derived from "Divan Lugat at-Turk". However, it should be borne in mind that these fragments are arranged in Fitrat's order. In

the "Divan Lugat at-Turk", the fragments included in the complex appear in the process of interpretation of a particular word. Prof. Fitrat classifies poetic samples based on their particular characteristics. While studying the fragments of the "Divan Lugat at-Turk", Fitrat first gives information about Mahmud Koshghari and his work in the introduction to the complex. Another important aspect of "The Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" by Fitrat, who has brought together the fragments that he has brought in different ways and has brought them into a complete work.

Another valuable aspect of the complex is the classification of Turkic languages. Many Turkic languages have been classified by our scientists. Fitrat gives the classifications of Radlov and Samoylovich from these classifications. Describing the shortcomings in the classifications, Mahmoud Kashgari considers the classification as the most accurate historical classification. Mahmud combines fragments of the Kashgari dictionary with both form and content. It classifies these literary fragments according to the following characteristics:

1. The prose sheet of the fragments.
2. By defining prosaic description, the scientist defines the theme of the earliest ancient literary monuments.
3. Contains them in content.
4. Classifies the literary type and genre.
5. Determines the characteristics of *vazn*.
6. Explains his thoughts on every event.

Fitrat combines fragments in the first part of "The Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" in 14 chapters according to the characteristics we have mentioned above. In this section, Fitrat discussed with Fuat Koprulu on marsiya "Alp Ertonga". In his article "Manshai of Turkish Literature" by Fuat Kusulu divided the four of "Alp Ertonga's" topic into four terms. Fitrat proves that these phenomena are not only four strokes but two marshes. The remaining two lashes come to the conclusion that "the other two lashes should be given another title". Fitrat divides fragments from Divan into two parts, the first part consists of quarters. His works are mentioned in short *vazn*. They say that these fragments are images but they are still picturesque. The fragments of the first fragment are combined by Fitrat under the following headings:

1. Winter-Winter Debate
2. About a war square
3. Summer Games
4. Hunting to battle
5. The War of the Throne
6. The Uighur War
7. Among the two merchants
8. Separation (hijrah)
9. Love fragments

10. Three Wounds (Five Pieces)
11. A war
12. The start of Dastan (six parts)
13. A *marsiya* (three parts)

The fragments are combined in terms of both form and content, and then a headline corresponding to them. The order of rhymed sampling was restored in the first and second parts. For example, the first three lines of the fourth part of the first part of the fourth letter in a rhyme come in a general rhyme. (b-b-b-a)

Qor, buzqamug'arushdi
Tag'larsuviaqishdi
Ko'kshin built urushdi
Qayg'uqbo'libo'krushur. [6, p. 162]

(All the snow, the ice are melted
In the mountains water began to flow
Cloudy clouds appeared in the air
They are walking like boats on every side)

After giving the quaternary quartet, the next four seems to be strengthening its content.

O'rdi built inkrashu (ingrashu)
Oqtiaqinmunkrashu (mungrashu)
Qoldibuduntanglashu (tang'lashu)
Ko'kraktalqinmangrashur (mangrashur)

(The cloud was blown,
The moonlight,
The nation is surprised,
Clouds are awe-inspiring!)

At the end of the quarters, explanations were made, which were incomprehensible.

Part 2 of the work is classified in this order. Only the second part consists of bicamps that are educational and ethical. They are merged under the following headings:

1. Advice
2. About visitors
3. Education
4. About beauty
5. An integral part of it
6. My advice to my son
7. Complaints about the world

8. For a loved one
9. He commends wealth
10. Teach
11. Praise
12. About wealth
13. To a deceived person
14. Separation
15. Religious advice
16. About the guest
17. It's about relax

Some of these binary elements in this section are large, and some are just a single line *masnaviy*. As the classifier counts, it also gives information about the period in which they are based.

Fitrat describes the third part of the samples of "The Oldest Turkic Literature Samples" in words. The scholar draws the dictionary of indeterminate words and draws their morphological, syntactic, and phonetic points. In chapter 3, Fitrat explains that in order to explain the words he needs in analysis, he has increased 3 sections. The dictionary contains about 130 words. In Fitrat's own work, Fitrat will focus on "AlbErtonga". It also deals with the debate with scientists. Scholar F.Koprulu, who has been studying the verses in the Divan dictionary, admits to "AlbErtonga" that there are 12 tracks. Fitrat does not agree with this: "...Alb to Ertonga" is a twelve fragment of F.Kopruluza. I think it's ten pieces. Divan's second volume, page 105, does not include the rhyme and rhyme, which is not the subject of "AlbErtoga". In the third volume of the third volume, on page 94 of the first volume, fragments are different" [9, p. 32]. And in order to argue his point, he quotes the following four:

**Yugurdikafalot,
Chaqildi qizilo't,
Qayurdiaruto't,
Sachrabaningo'rtanu.**

As Fitrat describing the "AlbErtonga" as a monumental work, "AlbErtonga" is interested in personality, explains the meaning of the word "AlbErtonga" and explains the causes of the mare's creation.

Today, Mahmoud Koshgari's "Divan Lugat at-Turk" ("Devonulug'otit Türk") was re-published. These publications were prepared by A.Rustamov, H.Boltaboev, B.Isabekov [6] and Q.Sodiqov, [7] and prepared for publication on the basis of S.Mutallibov's translation.

Fitrat's "Oldest Turkic Literature samples" is of great value. Fitrat's research on Divan can be regarded not only as an important event in Uzbek science, but also in Turkic studies. Fitrat's scientific experience should be continued in the context of modern philology.

References

1. Atalay B. Divanu lugatit turk tercimesi. 1-3 cild. Ankara/ 1939-1941.
2. Besim Atalay. Divanü Lügat-it-Türk ve Tercümesi üzerine Notlar / Kaşgarlı Mahmud. Divanü Lügat-it-Türk (çeviri). Çeviren: Besim Atalay. 5. Baskı. Cild I. Ankara, 2006. S. XVIII; Fazilov E. Kaşgarlı Mahmut'un «Divanü Lügat-it-Türk» eserinin Almanca, Türkçe, Özbekçe, Uygurca, İngilizce, Farsça, Kazakça, Çince, Azarice ve Rusça Tercümelelerinin Karşılaştırmalı Üzerinde / Turcologica III. – Tashkent: Vektor-Press, 2010
3. Brokelmann C. Mahmud al-Kasghari über die Sprachen und die Stamme der Türken im XI. Jahrhundert (Korosi Csoma – Archivum.) 1921
4. Koprulu F. Türk adabiyotining manshai // Milliy tatabbular majmuasi. 2-jild, 4-son.
5. Mahmud al-Husayn binni Muhammad al-Koshg'ariy: kitobi Devonu lug'atit turk (O'ngso'z). Istanbul. 1933.
6. Mahmud Koshg'ariy. Devonu lug'otit turk. 1-3 jild. (Nashrga tayyorlovchilar: A. Rustamov, H. Boltaboev, B. Isabekov). – T.: Mumtoz so'z, 2016.
7. Mahmud Koshg'ariy. Devonu lug'otit turk (Nashrga tayyorlovchi Q. Sodiqov). – T.: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2017.
8. Radloff W. Phonetik der nordichenturksprehen. – Leipzig. 1882.
9. Fitrat. Eng eski turk adabiyoti namunalari. (Nashrga tayyorlovchi Hamroeva O.). – T.: Mumtoz so'z, 2008.
10. Xudoyberdiev J. "Devonu lug'otit turk": topilishi, tarjimalari va o'rganilishi // Turkologiya masalalari. 1-son, 2007.